

SUPPLEMENTAL MATERIAL

Supplemental Figure S1. Fixed lactation curves estimated by Ali and Schaeffer (1987) for milk in first, second and third lactation using the complete model that also included Legendre polynomials of third degree for random curves. Dashed lines indicate maximum values during lactation (1st lactation: 85 DIM, 2nd lactation: 57 DIM, 3rd lactation: 60 DIM)

Supplemental Figure S2. Phenotypic mean per lactation day for milk yield in first lactation (A), second lactation (B) and third lactation (C). The blue line represents the LOESS (local regression) curve, grey shadings are the 95% confidence interval.

Supplemental Figure S3. Phenotypic mean per lactation day for trait body condition score in first lactation (A), second lactation (B) and third lactation (C). The blue line represents the LOESS (local regression) curve, grey shadings are the 95% confidence interval.

Supplemental Figure S4. Phenotypic mean per lactation day for trait backfat thickness in first lactation (A), second lactation (B) and third lactation (C). The blue line represents the LOESS (local regression) curve, grey shadings are the 95% confidence interval.

Supplemental Table S1. Estimated heritabilities for milk yield (MKG) in all lactation periods and lactation numbers

Lactation period	MKG		
	Lactation 1	Lactation 2	Lactation 3
1	0.429 (0.022)	0.358 (0.032)	0.271 (0.026)
2	0.589 (0.035)	0.468 (0.038)	0.424 (0.052)
3	0.475 (0.022)	0.409 (0.030)	0.366 (0.034)
4	0.556 (0.034)	0.508 (0.048)	0.388 (0.047)
5	0.561 (0.060)	0.468 (0.077)	0.379 (0.081)
6	0.495 (0.024)	0.486 (0.034)	0.459 (0.038)
7	0.581 (0.053)	0.523 (0.070)	0.434 (0.078)
8	0.538 (0.028)	0.602 (0.038)	0.482 (0.046)
9	0.575 (0.072)	0.499 (0.097)	0.379 (0.100)
10	0.551 (0.092)	0.519 (0.137)	0.401 (0.134)
Mean	0.535 (0.044)	0.484 (0.060)	0.398 (0.064)